

[Participant has already completed the consent form as part of the recruitment script]

Introduction

Great, let's begin! Please do not share personal information (like names or specific identifiers for yourself or others) during this interview. Our research goal is to understand how Rwandans use mobile money so we can suggest improvements to mobile money technology.

As mentioned in the consent form, we'd like to audio-record this interview to help us accurately capture your responses.

Do you agree to be recorded?

[If yes, begin recording]

General Use of MoMo

First, we'll discuss your use of mobile money in your personal life or job.

Do you use MTN MoMo, Airtel Money, or some other payment service?

- *[If Airtel or other] Throughout this study, we will use the term "MoMo" to mean [Airtel Money].*

How many years have you used MoMo?

Personal Use (Paying/Receiving)

Do you use MoMo to send money to friends and family?

- *[If no] Why not?*

Do you use MoMo to buy goods or pay for services?

- *[If no] Why not?*

When you don't use MoMo, how do you pay for goods or services? Why?

How often do you use MoMo compared to other payment methods?

Do you use your own phone or someone else's?

Is the phone you use for personal transactions a smartphone or a basic phone? If you use multiple phones, please tell us about them.

[If smartphone] Do you use MoMo via a mobile app, USSD, or both? [show examples if needed]_{dataset}

In general, do you have any concerns about your security when using MoMo?

- *[If yes] What are those concerns?*
- *[If no] Why not?*

In general, do you have any concerns about your privacy when using MoMo?

- *[If yes] What are those concerns?*
- *[If no] Why not?*

Have you ever shared a payment confirmation message online, such as on a WhatsApp status or social media?

- *[If yes] Did you hide any part of this message?*
 - *[If yes] Why? Which parts did you hide?*
 - *[If no] Why not?*

Use of MoMo at Work

Next, we will discuss MoMo in the context of your job.

Without giving specific names (so, for example, answer something like “clerk at a grocery store” and **not** “clerk at Simba Gishushu”), what is your job?

[If unclear] Are you the owner, a manager, or an employee?

[If no job, skip this section]

Does your business accept payments from customers using MoMo?

- *[If no] Why not??*
- *[If no] How do customers pay?*
- *[If yes] Are you the person who receives payments from customers?*

[If yes for receiving payments from customers, use “Confirming MoMo Payments at Work” questions below, either the “Employee/Clerk” or “Manager/Owner” version as appropriate. If no, use “Confirming MoMo Payments in Personal Life” questions below.]

MoMo Accounts

How many MoMo accounts do you have?

- *[If >1] Why do you have multiple accounts?*

Without giving names (so, for example, saying “my manager” instead of “David”), to whose MoMo account do customers send money?

Do customers send money to a MoMo account that you can access or to a MoMo account you cannot access?

[If cannot access] Without giving names (so, for example, saying “my manager” or “the owner of the business” instead of “David”), who can access this account?

Do you ever use or have access anyone else’s MoMo accounts? Without giving names (so, for example, saying “my friend’s account” instead of “David’s account”), whose accounts are these?

Confirming MoMo Payments at Work (Employee/Clerk) Questions

The next part of the interview will focus on your use of MoMo at your job.

How often do customers at your business pay using MoMo, as opposed to other methods?

When a customer pays using MoMo, how do you verify that they paid? Please tell us about the full process in detail.

Do you use a different process for different situations or customers?

*How often do you confirm payment **by looking at a phone**?*

- [if >0] Whose phone is it?

- [if >0] Is this a phone that you take home with you, or is it left at your workplace?

- [if >0] Do you always, sometimes, or never wait to receive a payment confirmation message on the phone?

- [if >0] Do you read the payment confirmation message or just wait for a notification sound or vibration?

- [if >0] Why do you confirm payments this way?

*How often do you confirm payment **using an electronic device other than a phone, such as a computer or point-of-sale terminal**?*

- [if >0] Where is this device located?

- [if >0] What information is shown on this device?

- [if >0] What is your process for verifying the payment, and what information do you look for?

- [if >0] Does the customer give you their name, phone number, or signature?

- [if >0] Why do you confirm payments this way?

*Have you ever confirmed a customer's payment **by having the customer show you their phone alone**?*

- [if >0] How often do you do this?

- [if >0] Does the customer give you their name, phone number, or signature?

- [if >0] Does the customer typically read out your name or the name of your business when they are entering the MoMo payment on their phone?
- [if >0] What percentage of customers show you an SMS confirmation (text message), and what percentage show you a USSD confirmation (on the same screen as the numbers for dialing)? [Show examples on paper if clarification is needed]
- [if >0] Have you ever doubted that the customer paid you even after seeing the confirmation message on the customer's phone?
- [if >0] Would any information on a customer's phone screen make you doubt that they have paid you?
- [if >0] Why do you confirm payments this way?

How often do you **trust the customer without confirming the payment?**

- [if >0] Why don't you confirm the payment?
- [if >0] Why do you trust the customer?
- [if >0] How often do you do this?
- [if >0] Does the customer give you their name, phone number, or signature?
- [if >0] Do customers ever say that someone else has paid for them? What do you do in this circumstance?

Are there **any other ways you use to confirm payments?**

- [if >0] Please describe this method
- [if >0] How often do you do this?
- [if >0] Why do you confirm payments this way?

To your knowledge, has a customer ever **tried to trick you** to make you think they paid using MoMo when they had not?

- [If yes] How frequently has this happened?
- [If yes] Without using anyone's names, can you tell me what happened?
- [If yes] How frequently have customers succeeded in tricking your business by not paying?
- What do you do to ensure that no customers trick you?

Has your company ever experienced any other type of fraud related to MoMo?

- [If yes] Could you tell me more?

Confirming Business MoMo Payments at Work (Owner/Manager) Questions

The next part of the interview will focus on your use of MoMo at your job.

How often do customers at your business pay using MoMo, as opposed to other methods?

When a customer pays using MoMo, who verifies that the customer paid?

[If they are the ones who verify, instead go to the Employee/Clerk questions! If they are not the ones who verify, continue here]

What is the process for your employees to verify that the customer has paid? Please tell us about the full process in detail.

Is there a different process for different situations or customers?

To your knowledge, do your employees always follow these processes exactly? If not, what differs?

*How often do your employees confirm payment **by looking at a phone?***

- [if >0] Is this a phone that your employees take home, or is the phone left at the workplace?

- [if >0] Did the company pay for that phone, or did the employee? Who paid for the SIM card and airtime?

- [if >0] Why do you use this method?

*How often do your employees confirm payment **using an electronic device other than a phone, such as a computer or point-of-sale terminal?***

- [if >0] Where is this device located?

- [if >0] What information is shown on this device?

- [if >0] What is your process for verifying the payment, and what information should the employee look for?

- [if >0] Does the customer give the employee their name or signature?

- [if >0] What happens behind the scenes to verify the payment?

- [if >0] Why do you use this method?

*Do your employees ever confirm a customer's payment **by having the customer show them their phone alone ?***

- [if >0] Why?

- [if >0] How often do your employees do this?

- [if >0] Does the customer give their name, telephone number, or signature?

- [if >0] Why do you use this method?

*How often do your employees **trust the customer without confirming the payment?***

- [if >0] Why?

- [if >0] How often do your employees do this?

- [if >0] Does the customer give their name, telephone number or signature?

- [if >0] Why do you trust that the customer paid you?

- [if >0] Why do you use this method?

- [if >0] Do customers ever say that someone else has paid for them? What do you do in this circumstance?

*Are there **any other ways your employees use to confirm payments?***

- [if >0] Please describe this method

- [if >0] Why do you use this method?

- [if >0] How often do your employees do this?

As the [owner/manager], do you audit the company's MoMo payment records, such as for a day or a week at once?

- [if yes] Please describe these processes in detail.

To your knowledge, has a customer ever **tried to trick your employees** to make you think they paid using MoMo when they had not?

- [If yes] How frequently has this happened?

- [If yes] Without using anyone's names, can you tell me what happened?

- [If yes] How frequently have customers succeeded in tricking your business by not paying?

- What do you and your employees do to ensure that no customers trick you?

Has your company ever experienced any other type of fraud related to MoMo?

[If yes] Could you tell me more?

“Confirming MoMo Payments in Personal Life” Questions

Next, we will discuss your use of MoMo when paying for goods or services. This includes payments at stores, markets, for motor drivers, and more.

Do you use a smartphone or a basic phone to pay for goods or services? If you use multiple phones, please answer for each.

Are any of these phones shared with other people? As a reminder, please don't use anyone's name in answering this question.

- [If yes] Do you do anything differently when using MoMo on a phone you share with others?

When you pay for a purchase of goods or services using MoMo, how does the merchant verify that you have paid? If merchants use different methods in different circumstances, please tell me about all of them.

Do merchants determine that you have paid **by looking at their phone**?

- [If yes] In what situations do merchants seem to use this method and how often?

- [If yes] Are some types of merchants especially likely to use this method?

Have you ever experienced a merchant confirming your payment **by looking at your phone alone**?

- [If yes] How often do merchants do this?

- [If yes] In what situations do merchants seem to use this method and how often?

- [If yes] Are some types of merchants especially likely to use this method?

- In detail, how does this process typically work? What happens when you show the merchant your phone?

- Do you have any concerns about showing your phone to the merchant?

How often do merchants determine that you have paid using a device that is located permanently at the store, such as a computer or point-of-sale terminal?

- [If >0] In what situations do merchants seem to use this method?

- [If >0] Are some types of merchants especially likely to use this method?

How often do merchants determine that you have paid by simply trusting you, without looking at any phone to verify?

- [If >0] In what situations do merchants seem to use this method?

- [If >0] Are some types of merchants especially likely to use this method?

- [If >0] Why do you think merchants trust customers in these situations?

- [always ask] Thinking about yourself, do you feel that you generally trust others? What makes you trust or not trust someone?

[Ask the same questions for any other methods they said they use]

Have you ever heard of customers trying to trick a merchant to make them think the customer paid using MoMo when they actually had not?

- [If yes] How frequently have you heard about this happening?

- [If yes] Without using anyone's names, can you tell me what happened in some of these situations?

- [If yes] From what you've heard, how frequently has the customer succeeded in tricking the business by not paying?

Have you ever made an error when using MoMo, such as sending money to the wrong person or sending the wrong amount of money?

- [If yes] How did you find out about the error?

- [If yes] How did you try to fix the error? Were you successful?

- Are you concerned about these errors? If yes, why?

- How do you avoid doing such errors?

Have you heard of any other types of fraud related to MoMo? [If yes] Please tell me more.

Do you ever hand your phone to someone else when using MoMo (for example, so they can enter their phone number)?

- [If yes] Do you have any concerns about doing so?

- [If yes] What are those concerns?

- [If No] Why not?

Next, we will ask you a few questions about your experience with agents.

Do you use MoMo agents to deposit or withdraw money?

-[If yes] How often?

-[If yes] What steps do you take to confirm the success of depositing money through an agent?

-[If yes] What steps do you take to confirm the success of withdrawing money from an agent?

Specific Interface Questions

We are 80% finished with the interview. Next, we have a short activity in which I will show you sample phone screens and ask you questions about them.

[These questions are used to gain feedback on their perspective]

- *Imagine you are a **merchant**. What information do you think a payment confirmation screen **must** include for you to be confident in confirming payments from a customer?*
- *Imagine you are a **customer**. What information do you think a payment screen should **never** include in order to protect your privacy and safety when showing your phone to merchants?*

Next, we will show you some example designs for you to respond:

- *Imagine that you are running a business. A customer who is a stranger pays you 7,500 RWF over MoMo. Because you don't have your phone with you, you will verify that you were paid by having the customer show you the confirmation message the customer received on their phone.*

[For screenshot examples [1,4 (a and b), 6 and 7] ask the following questions]

This is Example ###. Imagine that the customer showed you this screen on their phone.

What information would you look at on this screen to be sure they actually paid you?

Is there any additional information you wish the screen included?

*Is there any information you wish the screen did **not** include either for your convenience or for customers' privacy?*

How do you feel about this screen overall?

Would these answers have changed in any different scenarios?

[For screenshot example 6 ask the following questions]

Now imagine that the screen included a verification code that changed regularly to prevent customers from showing you screenshots of old confirmation messages.

How would you feel about this approach?

How often would you want it to change?

[For screenshot example 7 ask the following questions]

Now imagine that the merchant needed to enter a secret verification code on the customer's phone to make sure the payment confirmation message was real.

*First please imagine you are the **customer**. How would you feel about handing a merchant your phone?*

*Next please imagine you are the **merchant**. How would you feel about entering a code on each customer's phone?*

Finally, Imagine MoMo has a feature that allows your business transactions SMS to be sent to multiple devices that you can select yourself (eg. a clerk or shop attendant). Is this something you would love to use?

- *[If Yes]: why?*

- *[If No]: why?*

Demographic Questions

Finally, we will conclude with demographic questions. All are optional and you can answer "prefer not to say."

What is your gender?

- *Male*
- *Female*
- *Prefer not to answer*

What is your age range?

- *18 - 24*
- *25 - 34*
- *35 - 44*
- *45 - 54*
- *55 - 64*
- *65 or older*
- *Prefer not to answer*

What is your highest level of education?

- *Primary*

- *High School*
- *University*
- *Other / None*
- *Prefer not to answer*

In what city, town, or village do you live? [If Kigali] In what neighborhood of Kigali do you live?

That was our last question for you. *Do you have any questions for me?*

That concludes the interview. Thank you very much for your time!

[Compensate participant]